

Islamophobia: 21st Century McCarthyism Powered by Surveillance Technology

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ABSTRACT

Osama Bin Laden's decade-long legacy and its vestiges posed a long-standing threat to the Western superpowers, especially the United States of America. The fundamental target of this paper oversees the technological measures taken by the Intelligence Services to counter terrorism after 9/11. To investigate the attacks that took place on September 11, 2001, security agencies utilized extensive technological advancements to build reports through data mining. To gather additional data, field officers used devices to spy on persons of interest. The enactment of the Patriot Act mainly inspected the activities of practicing Muslims and individuals who demonstrated an interest in Islam. The paper examines the motives behind the early stages of Islamic extremism, the conditions of Muslims living in the United States after 9/11, and the efforts to dispel Islamophobic notions.

Introduction

“Two sticks, a dash, and a cake with a stick down.” What seems like an innocuous riddle sent from one individual to another presented to be an unforeseeable plot of the most significant threat on American soil since Pearl Harbor: 11-9 or as we know it 9-11. This riddle was used to telecommunicate between conspirators behind the terrorist attacks. That Tuesday morning, four planes that were expected to follow the course of their respective destinations made their way to the Twin Towers, the Pentagon, and Shanksville, Pennsylvania. The day terrorists infiltrated the security systems of the United States airports left an imprint on a global scale. It was a wake-up

call to implement substantial preventative measures in place as the lack thereof had given the concocters of 9/11 the means to hijack the aircraft. Shortly after, a series of protocols were placed to ensure justice and counteract terrorism. In a deplorable manner, people belonging to the demographics of the Al-Qaeda members were the aim of unreasonable searches under mere suspicion which raises the appropriate ethical flags and limitations as to whether security agencies should use racial profiling in investigating terrorism by technological means.

Immediate Response and Long-Term Effects

Over a month after the attacks, President George W. Bush signed the Patriot Act into law in order to strengthen national security and punish those obstructing the justice of the United States. It was a profound time in American history when lawmakers across the political spectrum came to an agreement as the Senate nearly unanimously passed the law. In contrast, the House had a larger deviation of opinion. Regardless, the passage of the Patriot Act deterred many terrorist attacks as according to James Carafano, a specialist in Homeland Security, added that 28 attacks were prevented due to the regulations (Hudson, 2012). The Department of Justice pointed out that it allowed the investigators to maximize the scope to investigate and prevent the range of terrorist-related crimes. Muslims on the other hand believed that it “allowed authorities to conduct surveillance... and let the government gain access to ‘many tangible things during investigation’” (Alshrari, 2019). As the crime-fighters went out of their way to preserve life and liberty, the effects of the Patriot Act were conceived as both volatile and violative.

The snowball effect of the Patriot Act introduced a necessary change to both aviation and national security but in the process outlined racial and religious disparities which negatively affected people of color and practicing Muslims. Investigating in such a manner violates people’s privacy and scrutinizes Muslims as there have been countless incidents riddled with fear and

anxiety around safety. As Americans' safety was ensured at the expense of both religious and national identities typically associated with terrorist organizations, it ostracized them from others. Additionally, it implanted a sense of self-hatred and further distanced them from their identities. Research would likely show an increasing correlation between unreasonable surveillance and searches of brown and Muslim people as the government's power expands. As the United States government expanded its authority to conduct searches, it goes without saying that power tends to be abused. People with their hateful biases have put it to use before to further their own agenda. Now the lawmakers and law enforcement are representative of the nation itself and so it is evident that the benighted masses would also follow their bigotry.

Origins of Osama - The Mastermind Behind the Attacks

The United States government's main objective post 9/11 was to bring justice to those who lost their lives by hunting down Osama Bin Laden, the leader of Al-Qaeda, either dead or alive. Born to a Saudi billionaire, Bin Laden joined the Mujahideen during the Soviet-Afghan war (1979-1989) in which he funneled money and resources from the South Asian-Arab world to fight against the Soviets. During this period, he created a global network and rose to glory amongst the Afghan freedom fighters through which he founded Al Qaeda in 1988. By the late 1990s, multiple fatwas against the US government were issued by Bin Laden for their hostility towards predominantly Muslim nations and greed for oil which led to destabilization of the Middle East. According to PBS which reported an unpublished interview of Bin Laden, "The idea was not to get involved more than necessary in the fight against the Russians... but rather to show our solidarity with our Islamist brothers. I discovered that it was not enough to fight in Afghanistan, but that we had to fight on all fronts against communist or Western oppression. The urgent thing was communism, but the next target was America" (*Who Is Bin Laden?*, n.d.). He remained true

to his agenda as a series of small or failed attacks occurred on American soil but a huge red flag looking back was when in 1993, the North Tower's underground parking garage met with an explosion by a small group of Bin Laden's posse. An article by the Diplomatic Security Service titled "1993 World Trade Center Bombing", stated how that particular event was the "first indication [that] terrorism was evolving from a regional phenomenon outside of the United States to a transnational phenomenon" (1993 World Trade Center Bombing - United States Department of State, 2019)

Surveillance Methods Using Technology

These warnings however were met with inconsequential responses although key radical Islamists were under the US' radar. The failure to adequately deter the events of 9/11 led to an irreversible taint on federal security agencies as terrorists attacked the US on a larger scale. Bush consolidated national security by gathering global backing to launch the War on Terror in the Middle East, while simultaneously proceeding to weed out the terrorists in the US. The legislators had to provide immediate revisions to the security system to grapple with the rising fear of Americans and prepare for incoming threats from their public enemy. Now the government can obtain private records of people via third-party sources without warrants and probable cause as doing so reduces the chances of alerting terrorists which keeps the investigation foolproof at most. With the growing use of technology, investigators looked into web searches. Satellite navigation systems were also utilized to get the precise location of criminals on the run and pinpoint potential hideouts. Members of Islamist organizations have specific demographics and people of the very same background were generalized to share

ideologies with the extremist groups or at least be more prone to align with them. After all, inspecting their activities will root out the bad apples.

The US government launched an all-out spy campaign on Muslims and foreign nationals. In 2011, Arab-American Yasir Afifi spotted a GPS tracker under his car during an oil change only to find out the FBI planted the device without a warrant. He frequently visited Egypt which raised a lot of questions for the government. According to “San Jose Arab American sues FBI over GPS”, it stated, “The FBI file identifies people he contacted, hospitals he went to, organizations he belonged to, religious services he attended and restaurants he visited with friends and family” (Egelko, 2011) but the court dismissed the case and declined Afifi’s request to delete his personal records from the FBI (Gerstein, 2015). In the heart of the attacks of 9/11, NYPD officers hired spies called the “Mosque Crawlers” who infiltrated mosques undercover under the assumption of homegrown terrorists being radicalized at the mosques. Mosque crawlers wore body cameras and listening devices to record regular people. AP News revealed, “White House funding [also] helped purchase cars and computers used in the surveillance effort” (PBS). Recently, in 2020, an app called Muslim Pro faced backlash for selling its data of users and their location to X-Mode Social, a location data software that then was sold to the US military. Muslim Pro provides direction to the *qibla*, where Muslims face the Kaaba in Mecca during prayers there are over 140 million users worldwide but its main users are from Western nations like the United States who do not have access to *azaans* a.k.a. call of prayers. Obtaining data in such ways, especially by violating safe spaces only creates distrust with law enforcement and technology as well, making practicing Muslims feel unsafe in their community. In fear of further ostracization, people have adopted new names or changed parts of their identity that may implicate them with terrorist associations. However, any attempts to reduce the stigma around

their identity proved to be counterproductive as it reinforced suspicions among NYPD officers. AP News also revealed, “David Cohen, the NYPD’s intelligence chief, worried that would-be terrorists could use their new names to lie low in New York... Reviewing name changes was intended to identify people who either Americanized their names or took Arabic names for the first time” (Apuzzo and Goldman). Muslim converts are not required to adopt Arabic names but those who do, do so to showcase a new aspect of their identity. However, given the circumstances that these security agencies create, they are not able to embrace but rather taught to cower or conceal their identity.

Such methods of obtaining data are not even foolproof because the basis revolves around a shared identity, not shared ideologies. According to “What is Patriot Act”, the National Security Letters that unwarrantedly allowed the FBI to obtain information via telephone records, computer records, and bank transactions, “led to one terror-related conviction” out of 192,000 issued NSLs (Drapkin). Similarly, John Ashcroft, former attorney general, promoted the National Security Entry-Exit Requirement as a counterterrorism tactic to screen noncitizens entering or leaving the US. The DHS stated that “referrals to secondary screening are not done automatically based on nationality... [it is] carefully designed to reflect current intelligence and respect civil rights requirements.” Despite their claim, this process disproportionately profiled identities of different ethnicities and religions. Individuals hailing from Muslim-dominant countries in Asia and Africa were required to register under the program and failure to do so would result in detention and at worst deportation. The ACLU stated that out of 83,000 convictions, none of them were linked to terrorist activities. Out of many who fell victim to this system, the American Immigration Council highlighted the story of Imad Daou, a Lebanese Christian who upon arrival to the States, a DHS agent registered him but failed to mention that

he is required to re-register every month or so. When returning from his travels, he was detained for two months due to his un-updated signature and eventually was deported back to Lebanon and barred from re-entry for another 5 years. This account is one of the thousands that dealt with issues as a result of a flawed procedural framework. What seemed like a pragmatist approach was revealed to lack substance and primed with subjectivity. Despite claims of not having prejudice, the works of security agencies further show evidence of structural Islamophobia and how it is endemic to the counterterrorism faction.

Legal Authorities Contributing to Islamophobia

The counterterrorism tactics focused on racial profiling which subjected Muslims to intensified stereotypes. Former NYPD Assistant Chief Thomas Galati claimed the extensive use of profiling did not provide many leads but rather worsened the case of police distrust amongst Muslims (Goldman & Apuzzo, 2012). The alienation of the suspected groups by the police also catalyzed hate crimes as the “percentage of hate crime incidents directed towards Muslims increased by over 500 percent from 2000-2009” (Racial Profiling and Islamophobia). Post 9/11, the steps taken to deter the growing terrorism were followed globally. Another article states, “Europe continues to make it difficult for Muslims to integrate and assimilate, ISIS will have a pool of disenfranchised and angry young Europeans from which to recruit” (Jamali, 2016) meaning ostracizing Muslims would only lead to the radicalization of Muslim youths. Additionally, the “The Global Order of Muslim Surveillance” stated, “China's digital surveillance state, in its current form, really only started to take root at the turn of the century. So, around the year 2000, 2001, you saw the Chinese police a lot more willing to turn to digital technology to gather data” (Renton, 2018). Evidently, the methods of deterring terrorism contributed to mass hysteria and

many have followed the example set by law enforcement and became vigilantes to target religious and ethnic minorities.

Conclusion

The Patriot Act threatened domestic rights to privacy by turning the US into a surveillance state through the use of technology such as fingerprinting, wiretapping, camera surveillance, etc. The legislative and executive branches of US have a history of exercising their anti-foreign ideas in turbulent times. Such disparate treatments include but are not limited to nativism, Japanese internment camps, the hysteria behind the Red Scare, and now the pervasive Islamophobia. These emerged during pressing periods but attitudes toward the targeted groups had changed over time except for Muslims. Though it has expired, this bill has residual effects in excluding foreign nationals and Muslims. Perhaps Islamophobia and xenophobia towards ethnicities of interest will decline as the threat of terrorism narrows. To reverse the damages, it's crucial to challenge anti-Muslim rhetoric, increase representation in politics, and educate others but the exclusionary aspects are profoundly linked to policies such as the travel ban in 2016 from 7 Muslim countries, making it difficult to disintegrate from American society. Maintaining security is something many individuals want but the system to investigate terror-related crimes was certainly not arbitrary. Consequently, many Muslims faced repercussions for something they had no hand in.

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